

Mining the Human Gut Microbiome for Host-Compatible Anticancer Agents: Implications for Natural Tumor Surveillance

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Background

The human microbiome secretes bioactive molecules that modulate host physiology. While commensal biosynthetic potential is established, the role of the microbiome-derived peptides in natural tumor suppression remains underexplored. Driven by the evolutionary host compatibility concept, we hypothesized that commensal peptidome harbors bioactive sequences that selectively suppress aberrant cell growth while maintaining tolerance toward healthy host epithelium.

Methods

We deployed a consensus-based workflow (several machine learning algorithms) to mine putative peptides sourced from the human gastrointestinal system in the AMPSphere database. Sequences were scored for physicochemical properties, predicted activity, and ease of synthesis. A 22-mer candidate was selected for synthesis and validation.

Results

The peptide exhibited cytotoxicity against human MCF7 (IC₅₀ ≈ 380 µg/ml) and murine 4T1 (IC₅₀ ≈ 430 µg/ml) carcinoma lines (fig 1a). Crucially, unlike non-selective pore-formers,

the peptide spared healthy human epithelial cells (MCF10; IC₅₀ >> 500 µg/ml, >85% viability) and caused no vascular irritation in the HET-CAM model (Fig 1b).

Fig 1. (a) MTT viability of MCF7, 4T1, and MCF10 at different peptide concentrations. (b) HET-CAM results (positive control: 0.1 M NaOH).

Implications & Future Directions

This study validates high-throughput microbiome mining for therapeutic leads. Future research could focus on:

- **Genomic Validation:** Investigate human metagenomic cohorts (e.g., TCGA, HMP) for the prevalence of the specific Biosynthetic Gene Clusters (BGCs). Correlating BGC abundance with natural tumor suppression or response to Immune Checkpoint Blockade (ICB) could establish clinical ecological relevance.
- **Immunogenic Cell Death (ICD) potential:** Mechanistic studies can determine if peptide-mediated lysis induces ICD. Quantifying the release of Damage-Associated Molecular Patterns (DAMPs) and subsequent dendritic cell priming could clarify if these agents could act as immune-adjuvants rather than simple cytotoxins.
- **Causal Assessment in Gnotobiotic Models:** To distinguish between direct cytotoxicity and host-immune modulation, in vivo efficacy should be evaluated using gnotobiotic mice monocolonized with peptide-producing strains versus isogenic peptide-deficient mutants.
- **Engineering of Live Biotherapeutics (LBPs):** To circumvent pharmacokinetic instability, a synthetic biology approach could be used. Engineering commensals with inducible circuits for in situ peptide secretion would enable targeted, continuous delivery within the tumor microenvironment.